

ECCO-V4r2 Data and SWOT Reveal Key Oceanographic Features of the California Current System

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Key Points:

- California Current System
- Sverdrup flow from ECCO-V4r2 data-set
- Thermal and wind velocity shear

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Abstract

The California Current System (CCS) is a dynamic and complex oceanic region characterized by strong, persistent coastal upwelling, complex circulation patterns, and a rich biological ecosystem. The CCS is of significant scientific interest due to its unique oceanographic features, which have important implications for climate, fisheries, and marine ecosystems. This study specifically focuses on the CCS and compares the contributions of Sverdrup, Ekman, and Geostrophic transports along the transect at 41.5°N . The analysis is based on the ECCOv4 data (Forget et al., 2015), which is averaged over monthly climatologies to understand the relative magnitudes of transports. The findings reveal that, on average, the flow in the California Current is primarily dominated by the Sverdrup and Ekman components. At the same time, as we move towards the interior (eastward), the Sverdrup components balance out the zonal geostrophic component. The contribution of Sverdrup without Ekman transport is negligible both in this system. Finally, simulated data from the Surface Water and Ocean Topology (SWOT) was implied to gain a better understanding of the sea surface anomalies and corresponding geostrophic velocity.

1 Introduction

The California Current System (CCS) (Fig. 1) is the most prevailing dynamic oceanographic feature located off the coast of California in the eastern Pacific Ocean. It originates from the northern tip of Vancouver Island (50°N). It extends southward to Punta Eugenia near central Baja, California (27°N), stretching laterally several hundred miles offshore into deep oceanic waters beyond the continental shelf (Hickey, 1979). The complex system includes the California Current, a cold, slow, southward-flowing current, and the California Undercurrent (Wooster & Jones, 1970). This deeper, southward-flowing current flow is opposite to the California Current.

Previous research findings on ocean models and budget analyses in the CCS have provided valuable insights into its dynamics and environmental impacts. According to Bograd et al. (2001), the CCS is a region in the eastern Pacific Ocean known for its complex oceanographic processes that influence the transport of mass, heat, salt, and nutrients. Various factors, including the annual cycle and interannual variability, influence heat transfer in the California Current System. In addition to heat transfer, it also plays a crucial role in transporting salt and nutrients. The salt budget, or the balance between the inputs and outputs of salt in the system, is influenced by various factors, including ocean currents, precipitation, evaporation, and mixing processes (Reddy, 2011). Along with heat and salinity, nutrient transfer in the California Current System is also an important process affecting the productivity of the region's marine ecosystems. Nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, are transported by ocean currents and mixed into the surface waters, supporting the growth of phytoplankton and other marine organisms. This transfer of nutrients is essential for the functioning of the marine food web and has critical implications for the ecology and productivity of the California Current System (King & Barbeau, 2007). Hence, gaining a comprehensive knowledge of CCS will enable us better to comprehend the local and global dynamics of ocean climate, leading to enhanced accuracy in predicting future climate science outcomes.

Our research focuses on the East-West transect at 41.5°N , which spans from -180°W to -124°W and includes the CCS. We utilize the ECCO-V4r2 dataset, which is a specific version of the Estimating the Circulation and Climate of the Ocean (ECCO) ocean and sea ice state estimate (Forget et al., 2015). The ECCO v4r2 dataset refers to a specific version of the Estimating the Circulation and Climate of the Ocean (ECCO) ocean and sea ice state estimate. ECCO is a data assimilation system that combines oceanographic observations with numerical ocean models to comprehensively estimate the state and variability of the global ocean and sea ice using the MIT GCM package. For our study, we

Figure 1. The location of the California Current System. The figure shows important currents, major regions, and geographic features. Courtesy of David M. Checkley Jr.

use the climatology data set to capture the repeating features of the CCS. We aim to calculate and compare the mass transport driven by the Geostrophic Current, Sverdrup, and Ekman Components.

2 Theory

From Vallis (2017), the concept of mass or volume transport can be explained as follows. Geostrophic flow is based on the assumption of a balance between pressure gradient and Coriolis force. On the other hand, Ekman flow is characterized by a balance between Coriolis and viscous forces. It exists in the boundary layer where viscous forces dominate, driven by wind stress curl. The Sverdrup relation balances Coriolis force, pressure gradient, vorticity budget, and wind stress.

For the calculation part, we assumed that the positive x direction is towards the zonal direction (east-ward) and y is positive toward the meridional (north) direction. The Coriolis parameter, f , is positive, and the fluids deflect at 90° to the right of the surface wind stress. The mean density of the fluid is denoted as ρ_0 . Now, if the wind stress is τ_x and τ_y in the zonal and meridional directions, respectively, after assuming the Boussinesq approximation, the density term ρ can be included within the wind stress. Thus, the balance becomes:

$$-f \cdot \nu = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_x}{\partial z} \tag{1}$$

Figure 2. Sea surface height (from the ECCO-V4r2 model) for the transect. The positive gradient till 136°E shows the location of the CCS. East of that is the gyre interior flow.

It is to be noted that, here, ϕ refers to the pressure gradient, and ν represents the meridional velocity. For zonal term u , we can write a similar equation by separating out the geostrophic component,

$$-f \cdot (\nu_g - \nu) = \frac{\partial \tau_x}{\partial z} \quad (2)$$

This subscript of g indicates the geostrophic component. If we perform integration in a vertical direction (from the bottom of the Ekman layer up to the free surface), Equation 2 can be expressed as,

$$fU_{ng} = \nabla \times \tau_o \quad (3)$$

U_{ng} indicates the vertically integrated non-geostrophic (ageostrophic) velocity in the Ekman layer. After that, we expand our equation using divergence and we integrate along depth followed by Vallis (2017) and it leads us to a Sverdrup relation, like this:

$$\int \beta v dz = \nabla \times \tau_o \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 is commonly referred to as the Sverdrup relation, which describes the vertically integrated North-South transport resulting from wind stress curl at the surface. This relation is applicable in the interior of a gyre, specifically towards the east, as viscous effects may dominate and render the Sverdrup relation invalid on the west side due to the presence of western boundary currents (Vallis, 2017).

Figure 3. (top) The velocity is greater in the CCS at -125°W . However, it shows a negative value at the surface because it flows in the south-wards direction, which can also be seen in Fig. 1. The velocity profile in the rest of the region is constantly negative. (bottom) It is to be noted that the color bar range for the upper and lower panel are changed.

Figure 4. The velocity is dominated by the Sverdrup and Ekman component in the CCS. The Ekman balances out the geostrophic component. The "interior flow" east of the CCS is consistent with the Sverdrup+Ekman.

Figure 5. (upper panel) A south-ward thermal wind velocity shear is dominant in CCS. (bottom panel) No significant thermal wind velocity shear in deep ocean

Figure 6. (upper panel) A south-ward wind velocity shear dominates CCS up to 100 meters of depth. (bottom panel) No significant wind velocity shear in deep ocean

3 Results and Discussions

The CCS is an eastern boundary current and proportional to upwelling winds, i.e., eastward Ekman transport from southward winds. The mass transport has been calculated for the transect, which includes the CCS. A clear sea surface anomaly is visible in Fig. 2, showing the CCS’s location and the interior flow’s starting point. The velocity profiles in Fig. 3, both panels show that the CCS is present and shows geostrophic features and features arising out of bottom friction. These panels are velocity plots. Higher velocity is seen in the CCS in both velocity and geostrophic velocity plots. Fig. 4 shows Northwards transport per unit length (m^2/s). This plot represents an interesting set of different types of transports at $41.5^\circ N$ in all longitudes. The model ECCO transport is high at $-180^\circ W$ and $-168^\circ W$ in the North Pacific Current near Japan. A greater magnitude of this current was later found in the CCS. It is to be noted that since Ekman transport is a concept, thus, only “theoretical Ekman transport” exists. In this paper, what we call “Model Ekman transport” is “Model upper-ocean transport” in reality. And this can most likely associate with other transports than Ekman because the model has more terms than just Coriolis and friction (Forget et al., 2015). Thus, while verifying that this model transport resembles the Ekman transport, we essentially validate our assertion that the Ekman balance will likely dominate the other terms in the model equations. The zonal geostrophic transport drops down at the CCS. The summation of Ekman and Sverdrup flow is highest in our region of interest.

Thermal wind velocity shear and model ECCO wind velocity shear are shown in Fig. 5 and 6, respectively. The shear is larger (and negative) in the column of CCS. The upper surface of the north-ward thermal wind velocity has higher positive values, especially between $-155^\circ W$ to $-150^\circ W$. For the north-ward model ECCO velocity shear, the upper surface velocity is negative up to 100 meters of depth. The thermal wind and velocity shear decrease as we move toward the interior. The velocity shear extends slightly deeper than the thermal wind velocity shear. Finally, we can see a clear sea surface anomaly from the synthetic SWOT data (collected from April 2015). The data shows this anomaly on a 120 KM wide swath spanning from $25^\circ N$ to $50^\circ N$ latitude. The highest sea surface elevation was noticed up to 0.6 meters. And the maximum geostrophic velocity found was seven m/s at the eddy’s core (Fig. 7, panels b and c), indicating the presence of a strong current in this region.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, California Current System was examined using the monthly climatological data ECCO dataset, and a comparison was made among the contributions of Sverdrup, Ekman, and Geostrophic components. The results indicate that the averaged ECCO dataset can capture the CCS, as it is a prominent feature throughout the year. Sverdrup and Ekman are the average CCS’s major components, as shown in Fig. 4. In contrast, the geostrophic transport remains almost constant in all latitudes at $41.5^\circ N$, including the CCS region. However, these mass transports need further verification. Adding the eddy kinetics with more details spatial resolution data set (e.g., Surface Water and Ocean Topography Mission) can possibly provide a better understanding of the dynamics. The velocity shear extends deeper than the thermal wind velocity shear, likely due to frictional effects. Although the present analysis suggests that the CCS can be captured using the ECCO climatology dataset, further analysis using monthly or daily averaged data is warranted.

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Figure 7. (Panel a) sea surface anomaly and geostrophic velocity plotted along with the SWOT satellite single swath. The swath is scaled twice along its width to show the anomalies. Panel b and c show more detailed images of the swath.

fox-kemper.com/classes/GEOL1520_19/proceedings/saneaakash_3.pdf) from the Spring 2019 conference proceedings were followed while completing this paper.

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